

ISic1171

I.Sicily inscription 1171

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR112059

0. [---]-----

1. τοῦ Πολυ[]νου

2. καὶ οἱ ἄλλοι πολῖ [---]

3. Ἡρακλεῖ

Edition: PHI140654

1. [ὁ δεῖνα τοῦ δεῖνα]

2. τοῦ Πολυ[ξέ]νου

3. καὶ οἱ ἄλ [ειφόμενοι]

4. Ἡρακλεῖ.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284915

EDR 112059
EDCS 39102325
PHI 140654

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0349 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5592

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